

P2GreenN position paper

on

EU Bioeconomy Action Plan

Bioeconomy is a *comprehensive and integrative approach* encompassing all sectors and systems that depend on biological resources, including animals, plants, micro-organisms, and derived biomass such as organic waste. This concept extends to the functions and principles of these biological resources. The bioeconomy interconnects land and marine ecosystems, along with the services they provide, and encompasses all primary production sectors that utilize and generate biological resources, such as agriculture, forestry, fisheries, and aquaculture. Additionally, it includes all economic and industrial sectors that employ biological resources and processes to produce food, feed, bio-based products, energy, and various services. The goal of the bioeconomy is to create a sustainable and circular system that maximizes the utilization of biological resources while preserving ecosystems and promoting innovation in bio-based industries¹.

The updated **Bioeconomy Strategy**², released by the European Commission in 2018, represents a comprehensive plan to advance a sustainable and circular bioeconomy, intended to maximize the bioeconomy's contribution to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the Paris Agreement. In addition, it responds to new European policy priorities, including the renewed Industrial Policy Strategy³, the Circular Economy Action Plan⁴, and the Communication on Accelerating Clean Energy Innovation⁵.

Whilst maintaining the initial five objectives of the Strategy (Ensuring food and nutrition security; Managing natural resources sustainably; Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources; Mitigating and adapting to climate change; Strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs), the European Commission introduces a third-tiered action plan to achieve them:

1. **Strengthen and scale up the bio-based sectors, unlock investments and markets** by mobilizing stakeholders, launching investment platforms, developing standards and

¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *A sustainable bioeconomy for Europe – Strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment – Updated bioeconomy strategy*, Publications Office, 2018, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/792130>

² *Ibidem*.

³ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-industrial-strategy_en

⁴ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/circular-economy-action-plan_en

⁵ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Accelerating clean energy innovation – Clean energy for all Europeans*, Publications Office, 2016, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/632213>

- market-based incentives, facilitating new biorefineries, and investing in research and innovation for sustainable substitutes to fossil-based materials.
2. **Deploy local bioeconomies rapidly across the whole of Europe**, supporting member states in **developing** national and regional bioeconomy strategies with ad-hoc facilities, as well as promoting education and training.
 3. **Understand the ecological boundaries of the bioeconomy**, implementing an EU-wide, internationally coherent monitoring system to track bioeconomy progress from economic, social, and environmental perspectives. This includes addressing knowledge gaps, enhancing observation, modelling, measurement, monitoring, and reporting capabilities, and providing guidance to bioeconomy operators.

The updated Bioeconomy Strategy thus represents a pivotal framework aimed at transforming the European bioeconomy into a more sustainable, innovative, and circular system. By integrating diverse sectors and fostering collaboration among stakeholders, the strategy not only aims to optimize the use of biological resources but also to ensure that these resources are managed in a way that supports environmental preservation and biodiversity enhancement. The focused actions and investments outlined in the strategy are designed to address current and future challenges, positioning the EU as a leader in the global shift towards a sustainable bioeconomy. This comprehensive approach underscores the critical importance of sustainability, circularity, and innovation in achieving long-term economic and environmental objectives, ultimately supporting the resilience and competitiveness of the European bioeconomy.

P2GreenN - Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows

Funded by the EU under the Horizon Europe Programme, the P2GreenN⁶ project aims to foster a paradigm shift, from a linearly organised resource and nutrient system within the agri-food supply chain, towards a circular material flow system between urban and rural areas thereby restoring the coupling of the water-agri-food system using a holistic symbiotic resource management approach following the **3R principle “Reduce, Reuse, Recover”**⁷. This alternative approach focuses on enabling nutrient recovery and reuse, through source separation of human excreta (urine and feces) and wastewater reclamation to produce safe bio-based fertilizers with the capability to replace conventional mineral fertilizers in agriculture.. This approach presents several obvious benefits: besides the production of recycling fertilisers, it can generate substantial savings in water and energy, and help to protect aquatic environments as well as water resources.

⁶ www.p2green.eu

⁷ Ellen MacArthur Foundation, *Growth within: A circular economy vision for a competitive Europe* (2015).

P2Green: Advancing the European Bioeconomy Through Circular Nutrient Management

P2Green's approach of coupling urban and rural infrastructures through the holistic management of water, agriculture, and food systems embodies the bioeconomy's goal of creating interconnected systems that utilize biological resources efficiently. By focusing on the recovery and reuse of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) from human sanitary waste to produce bio-based fertilizers, P2Green enhances the sustainability and resilience of the agri-food system and reduces dependence on mineral fertilizers. This initiative not only mitigates nutrient pollution from N and P but also promotes the circular economy by transforming waste into valuable agricultural inputs, thereby preserving ecosystems and contributing to sustainable food systems. Through its pilot regions and governance solutions, P2Green demonstrates how innovative, circular solutions can be operationalized, thereby advancing the bioeconomy's mission of fostering a sustainable, resource-efficient, and resilient European economy.

Given how well the P2Green project aligns with the European bioeconomy strategy, in this position paper, the consortium aims to highlight several points that should be emphasized and potentially included in the revised Bioeconomy Action Plan.

Recommended Actions for Advancing the EU Bioeconomy Strategy

- 1. Enhance the value perception of human waste**
 - a. Currently, the only reference to human waste in the action plan is "*Human waste, such as waste recoverable through wastewater treatment, is also a potentially very valuable and large-scale source of energy, fertilizers and chemicals.*"⁸ We believe this should be revised to explicitly include human excreta, in addition to wastewater reclamation, which we support.
 - b. To take an additional step, we propose a general rewording to improve perception and foster investments: using the term "*resource*" instead of "*waste*" (i.e., "*human sanitary resources*") acknowledges that human excreta are not waste but a valuable asset.
- 2. Develop standards for secondary nutrients and promote business models that foster bio based circular innovations**
 - a. Regulatory barriers to the use of *secondary nutrients* must be eliminated, and certifications and standards must be established to facilitate their market utilization.

⁸ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *A sustainable bioeconomy for Europe – Strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment – Updated bioeconomy strategy*, Publications Office, 2018, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/792130>, p52.

- b. Integrate a *market paradigm* that establishes true cost accounting and *includes negative externalities* in the Life Cycle Assessment of new products. This involves changing the pricing structure between bio-based and conventional products (in our case, establishing a level-playing field with synthetic fertilizers by introducing a tax on non-recycled nutrients or a tax on pollution) and implementing an incentive system for farmers using secondary nutrients, supporting early adopters with subsidies.

3. Promote local decision-making models and inclusive legislation for living labs

- a. Alternative business models for collaboration and resource sharing should be considered, such as the *hub-and-spoke model*. This model involves establishing a central hub facility that serves as a focal point for processing and distribution, surrounded by smaller satellite facilities or spokes, each leveraging local resources and socio-economic factors. Strategies and investments should prioritize local levels over national levels, as different scenarios apply. This approach will support the development of national and regional bioeconomy strategies, including those for remote areas, candidate and accession countries.
- b. Living labs are essential to develop and test place-based innovations based on ecological approaches and circularity in primary production and food systems. Despite the existing support, it is necessary to simplify legislative procedures for site-specific and product-specific needs. This will support a faster upscaling of blue innovation (high risk - high return).

Contacts:

P2GreenN Communication and Dissemination Team

Veronica Christofidis – christofidis@moverim.eu

Laura Vivani – vivani@moverim.eu
